

Phenotypic Screening of Carbapenemase-Producing *Acinetobacter baumannii* in Clinical Isolates

Renuka Yende 1, Niraj A. Ghanwate 1*, Tanuja Gajbhiye 1

ABSTRACT

Background: Carbapenem are last resort antibiotics used for Gram-negative bacteria. *Acinetobacter baumannii*, developing resistance towards carbapenem antibiotics called as Carbapenem-resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii* (CRAB), is an emerging public health threat. The well-known resistance mechanism is enzymatic degradation by carbapenemases, a type of β -lactamase enzyme that can hydrolyze carbapenems. This study aimed at phenotypic detection of carbapenemase activity responsible for carbapenem resistance in 58 isolates of *Acinetobacter baumannii*.

Methods: Carbapenemase production was detected by different phenotypic methods: modified carbapenem inactivation method (mCIM), EDTA carbapenem inactivation method (eCIM), combined disc test (CDT), modified Hodge test (MHT), and Carba NP test.

Results: Fifty-eight *Acinetobacter baumannii* isolates were screened for carbapenemase production using various phenotypic methods. mCIM showed intermediate results in 77.5% and positive in 24.1% of isolates, which were also eCIM positive. CDT identified 46.5%, and MHT detected 56.8% of *A. baumannii* isolates as carbapenemase producers, while CarbAcineto NP was positive in 50%. Only 24.1% of isolates tested positive across all methods except CDT.

Conclusion: Phenotypic methods showed considerable variability in detecting carbapenemase production in *A. baumannii*. The findings highlight the importance of using a combination of tests for accurate and reliable detection.

Keywords: Carbapenem-resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii*, Modified Hodge Test, Combined Disc Test, Carba NP Test

BACKGROUND

Acinetobacter baumannii is an aerobic, nonlactose-fermenting, oxidase-negative, Gram-negative coccobacillus that is most commonly found associated with healthcare environments. *A. baumannii* is a significant cause of outbreaks and endemic spread of resistant clones throughout the world (1). It is a major opportunistic pathogen responsible for nosocomial infections, including pneumonia, wound infections, septicemia, ventilator-associated pneumonia, bloodstream infections, and urinary tract infections. *A. baumannii* can acquire resistance to antimicrobial agents, particularly carbapenems, which are the last line of treatment for severe infections. Multiple resistance mechanisms have been identified, including antimicrobial-degrading enzymes, efflux pumps, target modifications, and porin deficiencies, which likely act synergistically (2). Compared to *Enterobacteriaceae* and *Pseudomonas* species, *Acinetobacter baumannii* is more difficult to detect for carbapenemase synthesis because of its naturally poor permeability (3).

Fewer treatment options are left for multidrug-resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii*. The worldwide spread of carbapenemase-mediated resistance has diminished the effectiveness of carbapenems against this pathogen. According to the World Health Organization, *A. baumannii* is a critical priority pathogen for the development of new antibiotics to combat antibiotic-resistant bacteria (4). *Acinetobacter baumannii*, which is resistant to carbapenem (CRAB), is a new concern for public health. Due to their ability to develop and spread antimicrobial resistance. Until recently, carbapenems were the most potent broad-spectrum antibiotics for treating multidrug-resistant (MDR) infections. However, their excessive use, particularly through improper prescriptions and in overburdened healthcare systems, especially in resource-limited regions, has accelerated the rise and spread of carbapenem-resistant organisms. Among these, the increasing resistance of *A. baumannii* and Nowadays, *A. baumannii* is a major worldwide concern (5). There are very few or no treatment options available for infection caused by *A. baumannii* (6).

Mechanism of Carbapenem Resistance

Enzymatic degradation is the most common resistance mechanism in carbapenemases, a type of β -lactamase enzyme which can hydrolyze carbapenems. Currently, Carbapenem-resistant *A. baumannii* is becoming more widespread worldwide. Therefore, methods for enzyme detection are crucial to prevent the spread of multidrug-resistant bacteria and ensure timely treatment. Currently, the identification of carbapenemase-producing bacteria relies on both phenotypic and genotypic methods. Phenotypic detection evaluates carbapenemase activity using conventional methods. These methods are advantageous because they are simple, convenient, and cost-effective (2). Thus, this study aims at the detection of carbapenemase-producing *A. baumannii* by using different phenotypic methods.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Isolation and identification of *A. baumannii* from clinical samples and its AST. A total of 58 isolates of *A. baumannii* were identified by conventional phenotypic methods and growth-based methods, including colony morphology, aerobic growth on Leeds Acinetobacter agar (HiMedia Pvt.Ltd., Mumbai), citrate utilization, catalase test and confirmed by the Vitek system (Biomeriux).

Carbapenem susceptibility of the clinical isolates was tested by the Vitek-2 system (Biomeriux) and Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method on Müller-Hinton agar (HiMedia Pvt.Ltd, Mumbai) using imipenem and meropenem discs according to CLSI 2020 guidelines. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of meropenem was determined against the tested *A.baumannii* isolates using E-test to confirm carbapenem resistance, and the results were interpreted according to CLSI 2020 guidelines (7-8).

Phenotypic detection of carbapenemases: Carbapenemase activity of all 58 *A.baumannii* isolates was detected by different methods

Modified carbapenem inactivation method (mCIM) and EDTA carbapenem inactivation method (eCIM)

In the modified carbapenem inactivation method (mCIM), a bacterial suspension was prepared using a loopful of inoculum in 2ml tryptic soy broth (2). The inoculation tube was filled with the meropenem (10 μ g) disc. The tubes were incubated for 4 hours and then placed onto a Mueller-Hinton agar plate that had been previously lawn-inoculated with a 0.5 McFarland

suspension of meropenem-susceptible *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922. Following previously established procedures, eCIM and mCIM testing were carried out concurrently for every isolate. Every isolate was emulsified in a 2-ml TSB-EDTA aliquot that contained 5 mM EDTA. The same protocol as for mCIM testing was then used to incubate and plate the isolates. Following an incubation period of 18 to 24 hours at 37°C, the zone diameters were measured separately. The results of both mCIM and eCIM tests were interpreted according to CLSI guidelines (8) For mCIM, interpretation was based on the zone of inhibition surrounding the disk inoculated in TSB alone. A result was considered positive if the inhibition zone measured 6 to 15 mm, or 16 to 18 mm with pinpoint colonies present within the zone. A zone measuring 16 to 18 mm or 19 mm with pinpoint colonies was classified as indeterminate. A negative result was defined by a zone of inhibition measuring 19 mm or greater without pinpoint colonies. The eCIM was interpreted only when the corresponding mCIM result was positive. The interpretation involved calculating the difference in zone diameters between the eCIM (with EDTA) and the mCIM. If the difference was ≥ 5 mm. The eCIM result was considered positive (9) In Figure 1 Ab 9 indicate eCIM larger zone showing metalloβ-lactamases (MBL) positive.

Figure 1: Representation of *A. baumannii* by mCIM and

carbapenemase detection in *A. baumannii* by eCIM.

Combine disc test (CDT)

The Mueller-Hinton agar plate was inoculated with a 0.5 McFarland suspension of *E. coli* ATCC 25922. Imipenem (10 µg) and imipenem/EDTA (10 750 µg) discs were placed at least 20 mm apart. After incubation at 37°C for 18–24 hours, the diameters of the inhibition zones around both discs were measured and compared. The formation of metalloβ-lactamases (MBL) was considered, that it was shown by an increase in the inhibitory zone of ≥ 7 mm with the imipenem/EDTA disc in comparison to the imipenem disc alone(7). In Figure 2, Ab6

represents ≥ 7 mm inhibition zone around the EDTA disk compared to the plain disk, indicating positive metallobeta-lactamase (MBL) production.

Figure 2: Representation of carbapenemase detection in *A. baumannii* by the combined disc test.

Modified Hodge test (MHT)

The Mueller-Hinton agar plate was inoculated with a 0.5 McFarland suspension of *E. coli* ATCC 25922, a standard indicator strains sensitive to carbapenems, using a sterile cotton swab. 10 μ g meropenem disc was aseptically placed at the center of the agar plate. Every test isolate was smeared from the plate's center to its edge in a straight line, and plates were incubated 18 to 24 hours at 37°C. Plates were analyzed as a cloverleaf-shaped structure in the meropenem disc's inhibitory zone where the test organism and *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 interacted (7) In Figure 3, Ab9, Ab10, and Ab13 represent the cloverleaf structure that showed positive carbapenemase activity.

Figure 3: Representation of carbapenemase detection in *A. baumannii* by Modified hodge test

Carba NP

In this test, two tubes are prepared and run simultaneously. The first tube contains Solution A, composed of phenol red, zinc sulfate, and water, adjusted to a pH of 7.8 ± 0.1 . The second tube contains Solution B, which is prepared by dissolving 6 mg of imipenem in 1 mL of Solution A. Bacterial hydrolysates, prepared using a Tris-HCl lysis buffer, are added to both tubes. The tubes are then incubated at 37°C for 2 hours. (Thirapanmethee *et al.*, 2020). When imipenem hydrolyzed into a carboxylic acid derivative in tube B, the phenol red solution changed from red to yellow or orange, indicating carbapenemase activity and a change in pH (7). In Figure 2, Ab6 shows the production of carbapenemase, as there is a change in the colour from red to yellow or orange

Figure 4: Representation of carbapenemase detection in *A. baumannii* by Carba NP test.

Results

Phenotypic detection of carbapenemases

Fifty-eight *Acinetobacter baumannii* isolates were tested for carbapenemase production by different phenotypic methods (MHT, mCIM, eCIM, CDT, Carba NP test). According to mCIM, 45 isolates (77.5%) showed intermediate results, while 14 isolates (24.1%) showed positive results for both mCIM and eCIM. As per CDT, 27 isolates (46.5%) were carbapenemase-producing, while MHT detected 33 of the isolates (56.8%) as carbapenemase-positive and with the CarbAcineto NP test, 29 (50%) of the investigated isolates were carbapenemase-positive. 14 isolates showed carbapenemase production (24.1%) by different phenotypic tests, except for the combination disc test Table 1

Table 1: Detection of carbapenemase by different Phenotypic Methods

Strains/ Isolates of <i>Ab</i>	mCIM	eCIM	CDT	MHT	Carba NP
AB 1, AB 29, AB 35, AB 44	I	-	+	-	-
AB 2, AB 16, AB 27, AB 34	I	-	-	-	-
AB 3, AB 15, AB 24, AB 36	I	-	+	-	-
AB 4, AB 18, AB 21, AB 32	I	-	+	+	-
AB 5, AB 19, AB 28	I	-	+	+	-
AB 6, AB 22, AB 25, AB 30	I	-	+	-	+
AB 7, AB 23, AB 26, AB 43	I	-	+	-	+
AB 8, AB 39, AB 45, AB 48	I	-	+	-	+
AB 9, AB 31, AB 20, AB 46, AB 49, AB 55, AB 56	+	+	-	+	+
AB 10, AB 17, AB 38, AB 47, AB 50, AB 52, AB 58,	+	+	-	+	+
AB 11, AB 37, AB 39, AB 42,	I	-	-	+	-
AB 12, AB 33, AB 40, AB 41,	I	-	-	+	-
AB 13, AB 51, AB 54,	I	-	-	+	+
AB 14, AB 53, AB 57	I	-	-	-	-
I = Intermediate + = Carbapenemase - = No Carbapenemase					

Discussion

The present study was performed to demonstrate the carbapenem production in *Acinetobacter baumannii* by different phenotypic methods. Out of 470 clinical samples, 58 (6%) *Acinetobacter baumannii* were confirmed phenotypically using the Vitek-2 compact system.

A comparable investigation was carried out by Abouelfetouh *et al.*, 2019 (7). A total of 74 non-duplicate CR-AB isolates were collected from various clinical specimens at Alexandria Main University Hospital, with 39 isolates from 2010 and 35 from 2015. Specimens included BAL (n=43), urine (n=7), blood (n=6), sputum (n=6), pus (n=4), mini-BAL (n=4), wound (n=2), and tissue (n=2). Most isolates were obtained during the fall and winter of 2010 and the spring of 2015, from different hospital wards. Identification was performed using conventional methods and growth-based methods, including colony morphology, aerobic growth on MacConkey agar at 44°C, and the Vitek system.

This study aimed to characterize 58 *A. baumannii* clinical isolates phenotypically in order to identify the enzymes responsible for carbapenem resistance. Several conventional phenotypic methods were performed, including the Modified Hodge Test (MHT), Carba NP test, Modified Carbapenem Inactivation Method (mCIM), EDTA Carbapenem Inactivation Method (eCIM) and Combined Disk Test (CDT). While phenotypic detection of carbapenemases offers advantages such as low cost, procedural simplicity, and no need for complex or expensive equipment, it is limited by low specificity and sensitivity (7). According to Bialvaei *et al.* 2021, (10), the Carba NP was detected more quickly and with greater sensitivity and specificity. Likewise, in this study, Carba NP and MHT gave effective results in comparison to other phenotypic tests for the presence of carbapenemase production in *A. baumannii*.

A similar study was conducted by Khuntayaporn *et al.* 2021(11) examined the effectiveness of three techniques for detecting carbapenemase, i.e. CarbAcineto NP test, modified carbapenem inactivation method (mCIM), and simplified carbapenem inactivation method (sCIM) for the phenotypic detection of clinically isolated *Acinetobacter baumannii*. Based on the results, a practical algorithm is proposed for the early identification of carbapenemase-producing *A. baumannii*, suitable for routine laboratory screening in resource-limited settings.

A parallel result was observed by Thirapanmethee *et al.*, 2020 (2) performed different phenotypic tests for the detection of carbapenemase-producing *Acinetobacter baumannii*, including the modified Hodge test, carbapenem inactivation method, combined disc method, double disc synergy and carba NP. As per our study, the modified carbapenem inactivation method (mCIM), EDTA carbapenem inactivation method (eCIM), the combined disc test (CDT), the modified Hodge test (MHT), and the carba NP identified 77.5%, 24.1%, 46.5%, 56.8%, and 50% of carbapenemase-producing *Acinetobacter baumannii*, respectively. A similar study was performed by Abouelfetouh *et al.*, 2019 (7). They observed that the sensitivities of the tested methods for this isolate collection were as follows: Modified Hodge Test (MHT) – 78.4%, Carbapenem Inactivation Method (CIM) – 68.9%, Combined Disc Test (CDT) – 79.7%, CarbAcineto NP test – 95.9%.

The phenotypic detection of carbapenemase production among *Acinetobacter baumannii* isolates revealed variability across the applied methods. The modified carbapenem inactivation method (mCIM) indicated a high rate of intermediate results (77.5%), with only two isolates (24.1%) testing positive by both mCIM and eCIM. The combined disc test (CDT) identified 27 isolates (46.5%) as carbapenemase producers. The Carba NP test revealed positivity in 42.8% of cases, whereas the modified Hodge test (MHT) showed positive results in 33 isolates (56.8%). Notably, only two isolates (24.1%) tested positive across all phenotypic methods except CDT, highlighting the inconsistencies and potential limitations of relying on a single method for detection. These findings underscore the importance of using a combination of phenotypic tests to accurately identify carbapenemase-producing *A. baumannii*. It is also necessary to note the alarming rise in carbapenemase-resistant *A. baumannii* in clinical settings.

References

1. Abbott, I., Cerqueira, G. M., Bhuiyan, S., & Peleg, A. Y. Carbapenem resistance in *Acinetobacter baumannii*: laboratory challenges, mechanistic insights and therapeutic strategies. *Expert review of anti-infective therapy* 2013;11(4):395-409.
2. Thirapanmethee, K. Detection of carbapenemase-producing *Acinetobacter baumannii*: the phenotypic approaches. *Pharmaceutical Sciences Asia* 2020;47(4).
3. Dortet, L., Poirel, L., Errera, C., & Nordmann, P. CarbAcineto NP test for rapid detection of carbapenemase-producing *Acinetobacter* spp. *Journal of Clinical Microbiology* 2014;52(7):2359-2364.
4. Dafopoulou, K., Vourli, S., Tsakris, A., & Pournaras, S. An update on polymyxin susceptibility testing methods for *Acinetobacter baumannii*. *Expert Review of Anti-infective Therapy* 2019;17(9):699-713.
5. Sharma, S., Das, A., Banerjee, T., Barman, H., Yadav, G., & Kumar, A. Adaptations of carbapenem resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii* (CRAB) in the hospital environment causing sustained outbreak. *Journal of Medical Microbiology* 2021;70(3):001345.
6. Jasim, M. K., Hadi, Z. J., Alsherees, H. A. A., & Annooz, A. Unmasking the Resistance: Detecting Carbapenem Genes in *Acinetobacter baumannii* Isolated from some Hospitals in Najaf and Baghdad. *Medical Science Journal for Advance Research* 2023; 4(2):101-111.
7. Abouelfetouh, A., Torky, A. S., & Aboulmagd, E. Phenotypic and genotypic characterization of carbapenem-resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii* isolates from Egypt. *Antimicrobial Resistance & Infection Control* 2019; 8:1-9.
8. CLSI. M100 performance standards for antimicrobial susceptibility testing 2020.
9. Gill, C. M., Lasko, M. J., Asempa, T. E., & Nicolau, D. P. Evaluation of the EDTA-modified carbapenem inactivation method for detecting metallo- β -lactamase-producing *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. *Journal of Clinical Microbiology* 2020;58(6):10-1128.
10. Zahedi Bialvaei, A., Dolatyar Dehkharghani, A., Asgari, F., Shamloo, F., Eslami, P., & Rahbar, M. (2021). Modified CIM test as a useful tool to detect carbapenemase activity among extensively drug-resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli* and *Acinetobacter baumannii*. *Annals of Microbiology* 2021; 71(1):23.

11. Khuntayaporn, P., Thirapanmethee, K., Kanathum, P., Chitsombat, K., & Chomnawang, M. T. Comparative study of phenotypic-based detection assays for carbapenemase-producing *Acinetobacter baumannii* with a proposed algorithm in resource-limited settings. Plos one 2021;16(11): e0259686.